

QUIZ**LAST NAME: MEYANBE****FIRST NAME: OLU****PROGRAM CODE: DSDD****COURSE CODE : ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (footnotes).

The author did use Zotero to insert references.

The author used the following software: MSOffice ProPlus

QUIZ: A SUMMATIVE ASSESSMENT

- 1. After narrowing down a research topic and to begin working on focused topic, the underlisted questions are relevant and worth asking except:**
 - Ask how the topic fits into a larger context (historical, social, cultural, geographical, functional, economic, and so on).
 - Ask questions about the nature of the thing itself, as an independent entity.
 - Ask *what if?* questions: how would things be different if your topic never existed, disappeared, or were put into a new context?
 - Look for questions that other researchers posed and had answered¹**
- 2. In essay writing, one of the key principles is to always cite the source of information or evidence presented in the research work. The**

¹ Kate L. Turabian. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations, Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*. Revised by Wayne C. Booth, Gregory G. Colomb, Joseph M. Williams, Joseph Bizup, William T. Fitzgerald, and the University of Chicago Press Editorial Staff. 9th ed. (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2018), 14-15.

following are the reasons why bothering to mention the sources of information in an essay except one

- because it can constitute plagiarism which is wrong and unethical
- because it is just not fair to take someone's work and not give credit to the person
- Not in all cases that a writer needs to cite the author or the source that provided the information being used.²**
- because it is a serious academic offense which can have serious consequences.

3. More often than not, researchers share their findings with the reader community. All but one of the options below are not reasons why a researcher will want to share the research findings:

- It is an academic practice to share research findings with the reader community.³**
- To tell the reader community of a piece of information they may find interesting.
- To let them know of an information that may help them remedy a situation.
- To inform of an information that will help them understand something they care about.

4. In academic writings, one important aspect to remember is to avoid being caught in *plagiarism* whether by act of omission or commission. Turabian further notes that some plagiarisms are not intentional but

² Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, 2nd ed. 2019. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1* (Bangui: Euclid University, 2019), 15.

³ Kate L. Turabian 2018, 9.

just carelessness on the part of the writer which can be any of the following acts except:

- The writer use ideas or methods from a source but did not see reason to cite it.
- The writer paraphrases a source and cite it but paraphrase too closely.
- Making a justification that it is practically impossible to avoid plagiarism even in small measure given that research work builds upon the work of other researchers.⁴**
- The writer used the exact words of a source and do cite it but fail to put those words in quotation marks or in block quotation.

5. **From experience and studies, data presentation in form of graphics are always preferred given that among other factors, it saves the user the pain of reading through large piece of data. However, sometimes there is the tendency to cause visual misrepresentation is which considered unethical. Which of the underlisted does not constitute visual misrepresentation?**

- Adjusting and manipulate a scale to magnify or reduce a contrast to fit the argument.
- Use of figures and whose image distorts values.
- The use of tables or figures that are unnecessarily complex or misleadingly simple.
- Keeping the figure simple for ease of grasping by the user.⁵**

6. **Several types of information are required in citation with a common aim of providing users with the necessary data that are required to**

⁴ Kate L. Turabian 2018, 81.

⁵ Kate L. Turabian 2018, 97-99.

properly identify and find a citation source. The following information are required in a citation except.

- When the writer quotes the exact words or paraphrase ideas associated with a source.⁶**
- Who published it and in what context?
- When was it published and where can it be found?
- Who was responsible for creating the sources and what title or other data identify the it?

7. From reviews, how to determine the scope of the literature review can be a difficult question to answer. The underlisted guidelines could in conjunction with researcher's judgement and advisor's preference serve as literature review guide except one:

- Include everything in the literature review section as bigger writeup somehow means better.⁷**
- When investigating a heavily researched and well-developed area, review only those works that are directly related to your specific research problem.
- A concise, well-organized literature review that contains relevant information is preferable to a review containing many studies that are only peripherally related to your research problem.
- When investigating a new or little-researched problem area, you need to gather enough information to develop and establish the study.

8. The interpretation and synthesis of the findings involve digging into the findings to understand what they really mean. According to Bloomberg and Volpe, typical questions asked by researchers that can

⁶ Kate L. Turabian 2018, 141.

⁷ Bloomberg, Linda Dale & Marie Volpe. *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Roadmap from Beginning to End*. (Los Angeles: SAGE Publications, 2008), 49.

give some high-level understanding of the findings include the following except:

- Given what I have found, what does this mean?
- What does this tell me about the phenomenon under study?
- What is really going on here?
- Is it necessary to listen to what others have to say?⁸**

9. Broadly, there are two research approaches namely; *quantitative* and *qualitative* approach. Which of the statements below is not true?

- Quantitative research involves the test of hypothesis and theory while qualitative research involves the development of theory, understanding and exploring of phenomenon.
- Quantitative research outcomes are broadly objective while that of qualitative research are subjective.
- Data analysis for qualitative research is as precise as data analysis in quantitative research.⁹**
- Qualitative data analysis can be referred to as the process of bringing order, structure, and meaning to the masses of data collected and following sequential order of organizing the data, generating categories, identifying patterns, and themes, and coding the data.

10. As indicated by Bloomberg & Volpe, analysis involves the move from holistic perspectives to individual parts whereas synthesis takes it back to a holistic view by pulling everything together. Synthesis therefore attempt to address the following except:

⁸ Linda D. Bloomberg & Marie Volpe 2008, 127.

⁹ Linda D. Bloomberg & Marie Volpe 2008, 96.

- to what extent the findings emanating from your data-collection method can be interpreted in the same way.
- how the research questions are answered by the findings.
- how the findings relate to the researcher's prior assumptions about the study.
- If a thorough analysis is done, there is no need relating your findings to the literature.**¹⁰

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¹⁰ Linda D. Bloomberg & Marie Volpe 2008, 133-134.